

Silicon Carbide Whiskers from Rice Hulls —A Unique Reinforcement—

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ABSTRACT

A process has been developed for manufacturing silicon carbide whiskers from rice hulls which are produced throughout the world as a waste by-product from milling of rice. The rice hulls contain the necessary carbon and silica, intimately dispersed, to provide a nearly ideal source material for silicon carbide production. The whiskers are grown by vapor phase reaction within beds of coked rice hulls at about 1800°C. Chemistry of the process is discussed, and the fabrication process is reviewed. The whiskers produced are relatively pure single crystals of silicon carbide, though containing large numbers of crystal defects.

The whisker properties make them attractive as reinforcement for various types of composites having high specific performance requirements. Applications in metal matrix composites are discussed.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Millions of tons of rice hulls or husks are generated annually throughout the world as a waste by-product from the milling of rice. For each one hundred pounds of rough rice milled, about twenty pounds of hulls are generated. Utilization or disposal of these hulls has been a challenge facing the millers for over a century. Landfills and open-stack burning were common methods used in the past, but increasing pressure for environmentally-acceptable disposal has caused the millers to seek effective, preferably revenue-producing, applications for this by-product.

The chemical composition and properties of the rice hull have intrigued researchers since at least as early as 1871.⁽¹⁾ Reviews by Beagle and Beagle⁽²⁾ and Houston⁽³⁾ present excellent and practical coverage of the applications which have received the most attention. Uses for the hulls, the hull residue and the ash include ruminant and poultry feed additives, filter media, insulations, panel-board, refractory bricks, silica and fuels. One particularly novel use cited by Beagle⁽²⁾ as conceptually possible was the production of silicon carbide. In Houston's⁽³⁾ update, this application was again cited as possible but not yet proven. In the early seventies, Dr. Ivan Cutler, working at the

University of Utah, experimentally demonstrated the concept and obtained U. S. Patent No. 3,754,076 ⁽⁴⁾ Work following this patent ultimately resulted in the discovery that sub-micron, near single-crystal, silicon carbide whiskers could be produced from the rice hulls. The prospect of a low-cost reinforcement with high specific properties has provided the incentive for development of this technology into a viable production process.⁽⁵⁾

2.0 RICE HULL CHEMISTRY AND STRUCTURE

A typical chemical composition of raw rice hulls and the accompanying mineral analysis on the ash residue are given in Table 1. The organic material is primarily carbohydrates (cellulose and lignin) and typically contains 8 to 10 percent by weight of moisture. The presence of sodium, calcium, phosphorous, potassium and magnesium are usually credited to the fertilizer and lime used by the grower. Other trace elements are present in the water used to flood the rice paddies, and some elements are present in the soil.

Since the earliest recorded analysis of rice hulls,⁽⁶⁾ it has been apparent that the ash content is significantly higher than for other cellulosic materials. Recorded ash content have been found to vary from 13.2 to 29.0 percent of hull weight with 94 to 96 percent of the ash being SiO₂.⁽³⁾ Recent x-ray and infrared studies have concluded that the silica is primarily amorphous and not organo-silicon compounds.

All results support the view that silica from the soil is dissolved and transported in the plant as monosilicic acid, and concentrated or deposited in the cellulosic structure by evaporation of the liquid transport at free membrane surfaces. This intimate mixture of silica within the cellulose has been confirmed as a near-ideal configuration for conversion to silicon carbide.

Hulls obtained from the milling operation are typically large, undamaged fractions of the total outer covering of the rice grain. To aid in storage and transportation, the raw hulls are often ground and separated into selected screen fractions. The most available fraction from United States millers is a minus 20, plus 80 mesh grind. The apparent density is greater than 0.7 g/cm³, but the bulk density is only about 0.43 g/cm³.

By heating rice hulls in the absence of air at about 800°C, most of the organic material and water are volatilized, leaving a carbon-silica mixture with small amounts of the impurities listed in Table 1. The carbon content can vary from approximately 38 to 44 percent depending on coking temperature. The apparent and bulk densities of the coked hulls are about 1.2 and 0.24 g/cm³, respectively.

Even though the coked rice hulls contain a substantial percentage of silica, the silica is not evenly distributed throughout the hull. Using a dispersive x-ray scan for silicon, the silica was found to be concentrated in the outer epidermal layer of the rice hull. More even distribution was observed in the low density core of the hull. Sharma⁽⁷⁾ found high concentrations of silica in the inner epidermal layer and, based on hydrofluoric acid leaching studies and x-ray analysis, he concluded that this silica was stabilized by the hull structure.

3.0 HIGH TEMPERATURE REACTIONS

The silica distribution within the rice hull has a pronounced influence on the silicon carbide morphology. The whisker growth is likely a vapor phase reaction and, as such, both a silicon and a carbon vapor or gaseous species must be available. Whisker morphology develops and grows during this thermal conversion in competition with the insitu development of particulates. Through the

adjustment of certain processing parameters, it is possible, within limits, to manipulate the relative amounts of particulate and whisker. Both configurations are essentially sub-micron in size and relatively pure silicon carbide.

With silica located in such heavy concentrations near the surface of the hull, formation of silicon and carbon vapor species are produced via the reaction,

These vapor species are then free to migrate as gases to the whisker tip and recombine to form silicon carbide via one of two reactions,

or

Whisker growth may nucleate at sites on the hull, on cell walls, or in free space between adjacent hulls. The vapor transport to the whisker tip must continue for the whisker growth to proceed. Growth from the base, although possible, is unlikely since such growth would require continual diffusion of carbon and silicon to the growth site. At the reaction temperatures involved, such diffusion would probably be too slow to account for observed whisker growth rates.

A different growth condition is presented for silica located within the interior of the hull (cell walls). Figure 1 shows the interior of the partially converted cell wall to be composed of very fine silicon carbide particles surrounded by a large excess of carbon. Two different mechanisms are operating to form silicon carbide particulates. A direct solid state reaction,

occurs because of the large carbon content in the cell wall. In addition, a gas-solid reaction mechanism involving the silicon monoxide intermediate occurs in two steps. Step one involves the formation of the silicon monoxide via reaction number one and step two is the formation of silicon carbide via,

where the diffusing SiO is captured by excess carbon before it can escape the cell wall to participate in the whisker growth.

The formation of silicon carbide from an intimate mixture of carbon and amorphous silica (the situation existing within the coked rice hulls) is in itself a relatively simple process proceeding via reaction number four. However, whisker formation involves a more complex series of reactions and transport mechanisms. The thermodynamics, kinetics, temperature, gas flow rates, availability and concentration of growth species, and silicon/carbon ratio are a few of the more important considerations.

Most of the silicon carbide whiskers produced in the past,⁽⁸⁾ were grown by reacting a silica-carbon mixture or decomposing a gaseous species in the hot zone of a furnace and transporting these growth species to a substantially cooler zone where they reacted to form the silicon carbide whiskers. Unlike these processes, silicon carbide whiskers from rice hulls grow in the voids formed by the coked hulls and within the porosity of the hulls. It is unlikely that more than a very slight localized temperature gradient exists between the reactants and the whisker tip. Figure 2 is an excellent example of the whisker growth in the voids of the hulls, and shows the high density of growth attained.

Kinetically, the thermal reaction of coked rice hulls to form silicon carbide is practical at temperatures above 1500°C in an inert or reducing atmosphere. However, the first tangible signs of whisker growth can occur at temperatures as low as 1400°C.

Being a vapor phase reaction, flow rates of the inert or reducing gases through the sample must be very low to prevent sweeping the gaseous reactants away before conversion to silicon carbide whiskers. On many occasions, limited amounts of whisker growth have been evident on the graphite crucible walls. Extremely long whisker growth has been discovered on the top of the sample bed where free space for whisker growth is infinite and the growth species are continually supplied by the sweep gas. For this reason, growth of whiskers in a vacuum is unfavorable due to the loss of the vapor species essential to the whisker growth.

Argon is the inert gas presently used for the conversion. Nitrogen can be used, but special care must be exercised in selecting reaction temperature and heating rate. Below 1350°C, thermodynamics favor silicon nitride over silicon carbide formation and thus nitrogen becomes a reactant in the process. A reducing atmosphere of hydrogen can be used but offers no real advantage, even though the reactions,

could help to increase the SiO concentration. A reducing atmosphere of carbon monoxide can also be used, but large concentrations will inhibit the reaction of the silicon carbide since carbon monoxide is a product of reaction number one.

Length of time for complete conversion to silicon carbide depends primarily on reaction temperature (kinetic considerations) and heat conduction. The reaction proceeds inward from the heat source on the outside bed, thus creating a radial temperature gradient throughout the system. Further, the reactions to form the silicon carbide are endothermic and the unreacted coked hulls and the product silicon carbide are relatively effective insulators. Both inhibit the conversion kinetics. Complete conversion occurs approximately four times faster at 1700°C as compared to 1500°C.

4.0 SILICON CARBIDE PRODUCTION

Producing silicon carbide whiskers from rice hulls involves three major processing steps: (1) coking, (2) conversion, and (3) separation. As outlined above raw hulls are converted to a carbon - silica mixture by coking and are thermally reacted at elevated temperature to form silicon carbide.⁽⁴⁾ The whiskers are then separated from the non-whisker silicon carbide and excess carbon by a wet process, dried, and stored. Additional conditioning treatments may be required for specific applications.

4.1 COKING

The first step in processing the ground rice hulls is coking or pyrolysis to remove water and organics. The coking is conducted in the temperature range 750-800°C in an air-free environment. Lower temperatures result in incomplete coking; higher temperatures could be employed if not limited by equipment considerations. During coking, the organic components of the hulls are broken down, and the volatiles containing H₂O, H₂, CO, CO₂ and hydrocarbons are removed. The off-gas has significant fuel value, and in large scale production would be used either to fire the coker itself or for other purposes. The weight loss during coking is approximately 65 percent.

The coking process is well established and should be readily scaleable. In the present work coking is done in a continuous rotary tube furnace. This and other type furnaces lend themselves well to bulk processing of rice hulls.

4.2 CONVERSION

Conversion is the term used to describe the whisker-growing step in the silicon carbide manufacture. Due to the high temperature required (near 1800°C), electrically heated graphite furnaces are used. In early work the conversion was done as a batch operation. However, this has now been developed as a continuous process which should be scaleable to any desired production level.

The reactions involved in conversion were discussed in Section 3.0. The converted product which has the form of a spongy mat due to the interlaced whisker content is a mixture of silicon carbide whiskers and particles and excess carbon.

4.3 SEPARATION

The whiskers are separated from the particulate silicon carbide and carbon by a wet process. The converted product is slurried in water, and then separated by a modified mineral dressing, froth flotation method. The carbon and particulate silicon carbide are removed in the flotation overflow, and the whiskers are contained in the underflow slurry. The whiskers are then dewatered and dried to produce a bulk whisker product for use in various applications.

5.0 SILICON CARBIDE WHISKER CHARACTERISTICS

The silicon carbide whiskers produced from rice hulls have the general appearance shown in Figure 3. Typical size characteristics and chemical compositions are listed in Table 2. The average as-produced aspect ratio of 75 is large enough to provide efficient reinforcement in suitable matrices, yet allows the whiskers to be handled, i.e., blended and fabricated, as bulk material.

Direct mechanical property measurements have not been attempted on these whiskers because of their small size. However, typical values can be found in the literature⁽⁹⁾ for similar materials.

6.0 APPLICATIONS AS COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT

The high specific performance properties of silicon carbide whiskers make them attractive as reinforcement for high performance composites. However, until recently, cost and limited availability have restricted the use of whisker reinforcements to research and very specific, small-volume, weight-critical applications. Now this cost-availability restriction is lessened for whiskers produced from the inexpensive rice hull source.

Silicon carbide whisker reinforcement of epoxy matrices has been considered, and may be cost-effective for specialized applications. Use of these whiskers to increase toughness in ceramic/ceramic composites is beginning to be investigated, though the potential in this area has not been established. The best established application for silicon carbide whiskers is in reinforcing metal matrix composites. Excellent results have been obtained, especially with aluminum in increasing strength, stiffness, and elevated temperature performance. A paper on "Mechanical Behavior of Silicon Carbide Whisker Reinforced Aluminum Alloys" is presented in this volume.

7.0 SUMMARY

A unique silicon carbide reinforcement has been developed. Manufacturing capability utilizing inexpensive rice hull source material has been established, thereby lessening availability restrictions. Applications in metal matrix composites are being developed which have already shown major performance and fabrication advantages. Availability of this reinforcement presents a challenge to develop new classes of cost-effective composites with significant performance advantages.

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FIGURE 1 - Typical transmission electron micrograph of a section of a partially converted rice hull showing the silicon carbide (dark phase) in the cell walls. Original magnification 60,000X.

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS OF RAW RICE HULLS
AND
ASH RESIDUE

COMPOUND*	WEIGHT PERCENT
RAW RICE ANALYSIS	
Organics	59.5
Carbon	18.8
Ash	20.6-21.7
ASH RESIDUE ANALYSIS	
SiO ₂	96.27
K ₂ O	1.10
SO ₃	0.57
P ₂ O ₅	0.39
MgO	0.35
Na ₂ O	0.25
Fe ₂ O	0.10
Al ₂ O	0.10
TiO ₂	0.08

*The compounds listed do not necessarily exist in the hulls, but are the compounds produced in ashing.

FIGURE 2 - Growth of silicon carbide whiskers on the voids formed between coked rice hulls (dark). Original magnification 200X.

TABLE 2. TYPICAL PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS
AND
CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF SILICON CARBIDE WHISKERS

CHARACTERISTICS	
Size	
Average Diameter, μm	0.5-0.7
Range of Diameter, μm	0.2-1.0
Average Length, μm	40-60
Average L/D	75
Surface Area, m^2/g	5
Density, g/cm^3	3.2
Bulk Density, g/cm^3	0.06
COMPOSITION	
Whisker Content, %	80-90
Particle Content, %	10-20
SiO ₂ , Si ₃ N ₄ , Si ₂ ON ₂ , etc. wt. %	0.0-1.5
Free Carbon, wt. %	0.0-0.5
Total Impurity Content, wt. %	0.05-2.0
IMPURITY ANALYSIS	
Elements Detected	Nominal Content (ppm)
Aluminum	200
Calcium	1050
Chromium	t
Copper	t
Iron	300
Lead	t
Magnesium	320
Manganese	480
Nickel	t
Potassium	230
Rubidium	t
Strontium	t
Titanium	100
Tungsten	t
Vanadium	t
Yttrium	50
Zinc	54
Zirconium	50

t - Trace Quantity

FIGURE 3 - General appearance of separated silicon carbide whiskers. Original magnification 3750X.